

INTERPRETERS AS SAVIOURS: THE IMPERATIVES OF INTERPRETING FROM FRENCH INTO ENGLISH AT THE SELECTED STATE HOSPITALS IN OYO TOWN

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ABSTRACT

The relevance of translation and interpretation is often limited to international conferences and engagements, literary translation, religious services and such like. Little attention is placed on the importance of interpretation at the hospitals where patients do not speak the language of the people of the community. This study centers on the indispensability of engaging French/English interpreters at state hospitals in Oyo town to enable French speakers in the town access adequate health care through interpretation. Two state hospitals in Oyo town: State Hospital, Oyo and State Hospital, Ilora, Oyo are chosen as case study. The objectives of the study are to: examine the difficulties doctors, nurses, medical laboratory scientists and pharmacists face in communicating with the francophone patients in the two areas; assess the danger that lack of effective communication can pose on the treatment of health issues of the francophone patients; highlight the required skills of potential interpreters of health services in French and English; discuss the roles of French/English interpreters at the hospitals in Oyo State with a particular focus on Oyo town. Using random sampling technique, ten francophone patients, five from each of the hospitals and six doctors, three from each of the hospitals; ten nurses, five from each of the hospitals; four medical laboratory scientists, two from each of the hospitals; four pharmacists, two from each of the hospitals will be interviewed. The Communicative Theory of translation by Peter Newmark will be adopted to analyze the craft of communication between the medical practitioners and the francophone patients. The study finds out that: communication problem is a major constraint in effective consultation with the medical practitioners by the patients; the use of signs and gesticulations by francophone patients to explain their health problems could pose danger on doctors' prescription; establishment of French/English interpretation unit will facilitate access to health care services by the Francophone. The study concludes that interlingua communication is essential for effective health care delivery. It recommends that interpretation unit should be established in all the hospitals in Oyo state in view of its boundaries with Benin Republic which allow the influx of the Francophone neighbours from Benin Republic and Togo into the town.

Keywords French language, interpreters, health care, health workers, state hospitals

INTRODUCTION

Communication is a major step in expressing and communicating health needs of a patient to a medical practitioner. Done expressly by the patient or on his/her behalf, diagnoses of ailments are based mainly on patient's complaints. Physical observation of a patient's physique alone gives way to assumptions that do hardly hit the baseline. This underscores the indispensability of effective communication of a patient's needs to a medical practitioner.

Oyo is an ancient town in Yoruba land. It is referred to as the Yoruba whose neighbours to the west are the Dahomeyans (Abiola, 1984). Oranmiyyan, the youngest son of Oduduwa and the most important was the founder of Oyo kingdom (Abiola, 1984). Oyo became a very powerful kingdom in 15th century and an empire of irrefutably great repute till 18th century. The kingdom spread to Dahomey, the present day Benin kingdom, whose founder (Onisabe) was believed to be one of the sons of Okanbi, the only son of Oduduwa. It equally extended to parts of Togo. No wonder, Yoruba people are found in parts of these countries.

The location of Oyo town is very strategic to easy access of the Francophone from Benin Republic and Togo. The northern axis of Oyo State has two main land borders to Benin Republic: the Kabo border near Saki and the Ayegun-Wasinmi border near Ijio. The two borders are less than six hours drive to Oyo town. Those coming through Okuta in Barutin Local Government of Kwara State reach Oyo town by connecting Ogbomoso to arrive the ancient capital of Yoruba land. Migration of the Beninese, and the Togolese (the Togolese get to the shore of Oyo State via Bénin, their neighbouring country) is occasioned by their search for fortunes. Majority of their men engage in farming while most of their women trade. The history of their origin linked to Oyo seems to be one of the soothing factors that aid their settlement in Oyo axis. Some of them claim to be kinsmen of the people of Ijio and Oyo town. The Sabe, the Nnatitingu, the Anago, the Boikon and the Goun tribes of Benin Republic most of them with unique tribal marks close to those of the people of Oyo feel at home in Oyo land. The expedition of Oranmiyan around 1000 AD to Nupe land; and Bussa where he took counsel that led to the establishment of his city called Oyo Ajaka or Katunga favoured the influx of the Beninese to Okuta, an Ibariba land in Kwara State which also claimed kinship relationship with the people of Oyo. So, the Beninese and the Togolese could access Oyo through Saki, Ayegun-wasinmi; and Okuta via Ilorin.

At present a good number of these migrants engage in farming in their host communities while a few number of their youths ride commercial motorcycles for survival. Hospitality and rich farmlands, Oyo people are known for encourage annexing them into the various communities in Oyo State particularly Oyo town and Oke-ogun areas of Oyo state.

Besides those living at different farmlands in Oyo land, there are districts in Oyo town where the Beninese and Togolese live: Atingisi district with more than hundred Togolese and Jabata district with over two hundred Togolese residents. In Araromi district, the Beninese and the Cameroonians are found virtually at every street. Hardworking and peace loving people, they engage in legitimate ventures to earn their living.

Lack of ability to communicate effectively in English and Yoruba languages to express their needs and feelings has always been a factor impeding access to beneficial healthcare services of these Francophone. Besides scores of private hospitals in the town, two state hospitals and five primary health centres under Oyo State Hospital Management Board serve the town. None of these hospitals has an interpretation unit to cater for the communication needs of the francophone

community in the town. This article looks at Health and language issues at the selected hospitals, interpretation exigencies and imperatives of French/English interpretation at the selected hospitals.

The two Oyo state hospitals in Oyo town are so selected for this study because of their strategic locations in the town. Oyo State Hospital, Owode, Oyo is less than 200 metres distance to Araromi district and about 150 metres in distance to Jabata. Oyo State Hospital, Ilora is less than 500 metres to Atingisi where our research population covers. The two hospitals are equally frequently patronized by patients of francophone descent from various farmlands in Oyo land.

Interpretation as Interlingua Communication

Interpretation is a bilingual oral communication. It uses resources of translating as a process but with peculiar variants such as immediacy of response whether simultaneously or consecutively, benefits of on the spot semiotics that reinforce understanding of the mediator's efforts, eye contacts and a host of others. It provides oral translation in real-time through direct communication of the audience needs.

As oral preceded the art of writing, interpretation preceded translation (a written form of interpretation with its peculiar features). It is a wonder that some translation theorists view interpretation as a sub-discipline of translation whereas interpreting activity dates back to ancient period of pre-writing model. In his view, Ukoyen (2001, 217) affirms that “ the very word: *interpreter* meaning ‘oral communicator’, goes back to the practice in antiquity whereby extra-territorial merchants always included at least one bilingual or multilingual person in their team to serve as a go-between (inter) in their business transactions with foreign merchants (pretres)”.

Kade, O. (1968) defined interpreting as “a form of translation (in wider sense) in which (a) the source-language text is presented only once and thus cannot be reviewed or replayed, and (b) the target-language text is produced under time pressure, with little chance or correction and revision”. Though Kade avoided the use of spoken languages to describe interpretation in his definition, sight translation is implied. Immediacy of passing and receiving the message depicts a real-time performance of communication between the players in interpreting activity. Interpretation is a translational activity. The utterance of the message as a source text and the reproduction of its equivalence in the target text enjoy alternate roles. In other words, the speaker can become the listener as the interpreter mediates between the two. In health care interpretation, it is imperative that the interpreter is abreast of the nature and symptoms of the patient's ailment. This prior knowledge will prepare the ground for further investigation and diagnosis by the health care givers.

In communicative chart of interpretation shared code and context between the interpreter and the interpreted for are key to effective message transfer to the receiver of the oral text. “Interpreting is real-time human translation in an essentially shared communicative context; the activities of rendering spoken messages in another language” (Franz Pöchhacker in Munday (2009, 128). The interpreter is a master of the two languages involved in the Interlingua communication: the language of the source oral text and the language of the target oral. By this he mediates between the two languages.

In healthcare settings, the role of an interpreter is pyramid. His baseline function is to convert the message from the patient to the health care provider and vice-versa. Aided by visible dispositions, he clarifies the message and mediates the cultural exigencies that usually feature while accessing health care facilities in the hospitals. One distinct characteristic of interpretation is the interpreter's consciousness of his audience. Lederer (1994, 17) affirms that “...présent aux circonstances

d'émission et de réception de la parole, l'interprète constate que l'orateur a conscience de ses auditeurs et leur adapte la formulation de sa pensée". The speaker watches the reaction of the listener and could likely judge if his thoughts expressed in words to the interpreter are well transcoded by the latter.

In essence, interpreting is not linguistic transcoding but a process based on knowledge-based comprehension (Munday 2009, 130). This underscores the importance of good knowledge of not only the linguistic behavior of the two languages but also the extra linguistic meaning of what the utterances imply. The health caregiver and the patient look up to the interpreter to mediate the message accurately in order to ensure right diagnosis and treatment of the patient's ailments. From the social stand point therefore, the interpreter is seen as a mediator not only between languages but also between cultures and value systems.

Interpretation is a cognitive processing activity. Human mental quick recording, processing and reproduction of the speaker's message are a unique feature of interpretation. It is generally believed that interpreters draw on insights and methods deployed in cognitive psychology, psycholinguistics and cognitive pragmatics (Poyatos, 1987). Two main types are identifiable: simultaneous and consecutive interpretations. Simultaneous interpretation is oral mediation of immediacy in translation activity. The speaker gives his message in units of words and the intermediary gives the sense at the same time. It is difficult to determine the time lag between the processing and reproduction. In the words of Lederer (1986): "les activités exigées par la traduction simultanée sont multiples. En même temps que l'interprète entend le discours, il perçoit la situation globale...; en même temps qu'il conceptualise ce qu'il vient d'entendre, il entend la suite et énonce le résultat de son opération de conceptualization, il écoute ce qu'il dit lui-même pour vérifier la correction de son expression". In other words, simultaneous interpreter listens to the speech and at the same time views it as a whole, conceptualizes what he has listened to at the same time and delivers the speech in the language of his audience. He, at the same time, listens to himself to check the correctness of his product.

The second major type of interpretation is Consecutive Interpretation. The speaker gives his speech in units of sense allowing the interpreter to take notes of key points. The time lag is often appreciable. This type of interpretation occurs often in conference interpretation. The interpreter, consecutive or simultaneous, draws meanings from multiple of words spoken by the author of the message and not from the linguistic forms with which he passes his ideas. Consecutive interpretation uses a memory that retains for a long time deverbaised thoughts of the speech author. In translation class with my students of second degree in university, I often distinguish how simultaneous interpretation is different from the consecutive one through illustration with the two popular pastors of the two leading gospel churches in Nigeria: The Deeper Christian Life Ministry and The Redeemed Christian Church of God. Pastor Kumuyi of Deeper Life preaches at his pace without seeming to be conscious of interpreters as scores of interpreters render the same message in their own languages to their own language audience. As Kumuyi would not wait for anyone, the interpreters are obliged to interpret simultaneously as their pastor gives the *word* at his own pace. Pastor Adeboye of the Redeemed Church talks slowly and in units of sense. The interpreter allows him to finish a unit of sense before reproducing the same in the language of his audience. Sometimes the pastor corrects the interpreter when he betrays the spirit of his speech.

Interpretation in health care services makes use of both types of interpretation. In an emergency case where the interpreter may not have allowance of pre-investigation of the patient's health

conditions, simultaneous interpretation must be deplored. This demands a high cognitive mental accuracy of sense if wrong diagnosis and prescriptions will not arise from misinformation. In a situation where ample time is allowed to interact with the patient, the interpreter takes down notes of the patient's complaints. As he interprets the complaints to the medical practitioner and the examination ensues between the patient and the former, the interpreter assumes simultaneous role.

State Hospitals in Oyo and the Francophone patients

Since records are not available that before now efforts were made to research into frequency of patients of French speaking communities in the hospitals under study and the statistics of such patients in the hospitals, we would rely on the oral interview with the francophone patients and questionnaires completed by doctors, nurses, medical laboratory scientists, pharmacists, administrative staff, ward orderly and radiologists.

Oyo State Hospital Management Board has state hospitals and primary health centres located virtually in all towns and villages in the state to cater for the health needs of the citizens. The hospitals render out-patient services to all patients of varying ailments. Patients who dwell in remote farmlands where hospitals or health centres are not built come to the nearby towns or villages where health facilities could be accessed.

Majority of the Francophone people in Oyo state engage in farming and trading. While men work mainly as labourers for the indigenes, their women either support their men on the farms or trade. Despite long years of living among the Yoruba people of Oyo, majority of them have shaky understanding of Yoruba language. Besides expressions of daily communication in Yoruba with their host, they can hardly express their health feelings in the language. This challenge always necessitates the intervention of an interpreter who is vast in French and English languages.

Unlike in French and Francophone systems of education where English language is a compulsory subject to be learned by students from primary to secondary levels of education in the curricular, French language does not enjoy the same status in Nigeria education system. Consequently, it is very rare to get a medical practitioner in the hospitals with the understanding of French language. To attend to patients who could only express themselves in French language, the hospital staff face serious problem of communication. Most of the friends or relatives that accompany the patients to the hospitals cannot express themselves clearly and coherently in English or Yoruba to help in the diagnosis of the health challenges of the patients by the doctors.

Statement of the problem

Effective communication is often effortless with communicative agents that share similar code. A lot of loss of sense ensues where understanding the message is a matter of semiotic description. The Francophone in Oyo town desiring access to health care services in Oyo State Hospitals in the town find it difficult to express symptoms of their health problems clearly due to language barrier as most of them could only speak French language effectively. The study investigates how health workers in the hospitals view the importance of interpretation from French into English stemmed from their daily encounter with the patients.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study is to examine the difficulties doctors, nurses, medical laboratory scientists and pharmacists face in communicating with the francophone patients in the two areas of our study. Specifically the study:

- i. assesses the danger that lack of effective communication can pose on treatment of health issues of the francophone patients;
- ii. highlight the required skills of the potential English/French interpreters of health services;
- iii. discuss the roles of French/English interpreters at the State Hospitals in Oyo state with a particular focus on Oyo town.

Research questions

The following research questions were raised:

- i. How often do you have patients that could only express themselves effectively in French?
- ii. Has there ever been difficulty in understanding the need(s) of the patients without an interpreter?
- iii. Can an interpreter hasten the understanding of the patient's health problems by the health workers?
- iv. Without an interpreter, can there be any error of prescription when diagnosis is based on assumption?
- v. Is it expedient to have an interpretation unit in the hospital to cater for the francophone patients residing in Oyo land?

Research Method

Random sampling technique was used for the study; the population for the study consisted of the hospital workers from the two hospitals in Oyo town. The sample includes one hundred (100) hospital workers. They were selected through simple random sampling technique: ten (10) francophone patients, twenty (20) doctors, twenty (20) nurses, ten (10) pharmacists, ten (10) medical laboratory scientists, ten (10) laboratory technicians, ten (10) administrative staff, and ten (10) ward orderly. They were selected from the two hospitals and they were all termed to be hospital workers. Self-designed questionnaire titled: Interpreters as Saviours, Interpreting from French to English (ISIFE) was administered to elicit information on communication with Francophone patients and needs for professional interpreters. The data collected were analysed using simple percentage and frequency counts. Peter Newmark's communicative theory of translation was used to allude to the essentials of clear transfer of message from one language into another.

Data Analysis and Results

Research question 1: How have you been attending and communicating with patients that could only express themselves effectively in French language?

Table 1: showing hospital workers attending and communicating with patients that could only express themselves effectively in French language.

SN	ITEMS	YES	%	NO	%	TOTAL
Attending and communicating with Francophone patients						
1	I often attend to francophone patients in the hospital	80	80	20	20	100
2	Misunderstanding medical instructions is common with francophone patients	90	90	10	10	100
3	Language barriers make communication with francophone patients difficult	90	10	10	10	100
4	Francophone patients often find it difficult to explain their symptoms clearly	80	80	20	20	100
5	I have witnessed cases where a patient’s health was negatively affected due to language barrier	90	90	10	10	100

The table shows that 80 (80%) medical officers and hospital workers in the two hospitals often attend to francophone patients in the hospital while 20 (20%) do not. 90 (90%) hospital workers explained that misunderstanding medical instructions is common with the francophone patients, while 10 (10%) did not agree. 90 (90%) hospital workers said that language barriers make communication with francophone patients difficult while 10 (10%) did not agree. 80 (80%) hospital workers declared that francophone patients often find it difficult to explain their symptoms clearly. 20 (20%) did not so agree. 90 (90%) hospital workers stated that they have witnessed cases where a patient’s health was negatively affected due to language barrier, while 10 (10%) did not have similar experience.

Research question 2: Has there ever been difficulty in understanding the need (s) of patients without interpreter?

Table 2: showing difficulty in understanding the need(s) of patients without an interpreter.

SN	ITEMS	YES	%	NO	%	TOTAL
Danger of assumptions during consultation						
1	There is always interpreter in the hospital to interpret French language	02	02	98	98	100
2	In the absence of interpreter, I usually rely on assumptions when consulting francophone patients	95	95	05	05	100
3	Making assumptions during consultation can lead to wrong diagnosis	100	100	00	00	100
4	Assumptions during consultations can delay proper treatment	100	100	100	100	100
5	Wrong prescriptions may result from miscommunication with non-native speakers	95	05	05	05	100

Table 2 shows that 02 (2%) hospital workers agreed that there is always interpreter in the hospital to interpret French language while 98 (98%) disagreed. 95 (95%) hospital workers said that in the absence of interpretation; they usually rely on assumptions when consulting francophone patients while 5 (5%) did not agree. 100 (100%) hospital workers agreed that making assumptions during consultation can lead to wrong diagnosis. 100 (100%) hospital workers also; agreed that assumptions during consultation can delay proper treatment. 95 (95%) hospital workers explained that wrong prescriptions seem to result from miscommunication with non-native speakers while 5 (5%) did not agree.

Research question 3: Can interpreter hasten the understanding of patients' health problems by the health workers?

Table 3 showing health workers declaring that interpreter can hasten the understanding of patients' health problems.

SN	ITEMS	YES	%	NO	%	TOTAL
Companion Interpretation						
1	Francophone patients usually come with companions to help with interpretation	10	10	90	90	100
2	Communications are not always reliable in interpreting patients' health problems	100	100	–	–	100
3	Relying on companions for interpretation can lead to incomplete information	100	100	–	–	100
4	The use of companions as interpreters breaches patient confidentiality	90	90	10	10	100
5	Distortion of medical facts may occur when companions interpret	80	80	20	20	100

The table shows that 10 (10%) hospital workers agreed that francophone patients usually come with companions to help them with communication while 90 (90%) did not. 100 (100%) hospital workers said that companions were not always reliable in interpreting patients' health problems. 100 (100%) agreed that relying on companions for interpretation can lead to incomplete information. 95 (95%) hospital workers said distortion of medical facts may occur when companions interpret while 5 (5%) did not agree.

Research Question 4: With interpreter; and having interpretation unit in the hospital, can there be any error of prescription when diagnosis is based on assumption.

Table 4: showing that with interpreter and having interpretation unit in the hospital, there would be no error of prescription when diagnosis is not based on assumption.

SN	ITEMS	YES	%	NO	%	TOTAL
	Need for Professional Interpreters					
1	Interpreters will make consultation with francophone patients faster and easier	100	100	–	–	100
2	There is a strong need for professional French/English interpreters in hospitals in Oyo town	100	100	–	–	100
3	The use of interpreters will reduce medical errors	100	100	–	–	100
4	Professional interpreters will help ensure accurate communication between health workers and francophone patients	100	100	–	–	100
5	The presence of professional interpreters will improve patient satisfaction and healthcare delivery	100	100	–	–	100

The table shows 100 (100%) francophone patients agreed that interpreters will make consultation with health workers faster and easier. 100 (100%) francophone patients said that there was a strong need for professional French/English interpreters in hospitals in Oyo town. 100 (100%) francophone patients said that the use of interpreters would reduce medical errors. 100 (100%) francophone patients supported that professional interpreters would help ensure accurate communication between them and health workers. 100 (100%) francophone patients declared that the presence of professional interpreters would improve patients satisfaction and healthcare delivery.

Imperatives of French-English Interpretation at the State Hospitals in Oyo Town

For empirical analysis of the plight of the medical practitioners before Francophone patients, our questionnaires were structured under four sections: communication with the francophone patients; danger of assumption during consultation, companion mediation; and need for professional interpreters. The findings of the study revealed that medical officers and hospital workers in the two hospitals often attend to francophone patients in the hospital. The study revealed that Hospital workers detected that language barriers make communication with francophone patients difficult. Furthermore, the study revealed that wrong prescriptions could result from miscommunication with non-native speakers. It was concluded that, having interpreters in the hospitals would make consultation with health workers faster and easier and that the use of interpreters would reduce medical errors. Likewise, francophone patients supported that having professional interpreters would help ensure accurate communication between them and health workers and this would improve patients' satisfaction and healthcare delivery which will in turn improve patients' satisfaction and healthcare delivery.

Hundred questionnaire items were distributed to the two hospitals under study. Doctors, nurses, medical laboratory scientists, pharmacists, administrative staff, ward orderly, laboratory technician and pharmacist technologists served as respondents.

As could be seen above, eighty (80) out of one hundred (100) respondents stated that they occasionally attended to patients of francophone extraction possibly once in two weeks. This suggests that though the frequency rate of the patients at the hospitals is low their patronage is significant. It underlies the need and basis for effective communication between them and the medical practitioners in the hospitals.

On whether misunderstanding of medical instructions is common with the francophone patients in the hospitals or not, ninety-eight respondents agreed that patients of this category have difficulty in understanding medical instructions in English or Yoruba. Where patients should take medications before or after meal, the language barrier could lead to misuse or involuntary abuse of the drugs. In cases where they were expected to return to the hospitals for injection, most of them could skip days of injection as sign language could hardly help in passing the instructions.

All the respondents agreed that language barrier made communication with francophone patients difficult. It often takes longer period to attend to non-speaker of English or Yoruba in the hospitals than the natives who speak either of the languages. Since all the staff of the hospitals agreed that language was a barrier to effective communication; from the file management staff, to the doctor; from the doctor to the medical laboratory scientist to the doctor; from the doctor to the pharmacist; from the pharmacist to the nurses; from the nurses to other staff, attending to francophone patients in the hospitals was a herculean task because of inability to have a flow of communication between the health care givers and the sick.

The first step to accessing health facilities by any patient is the ability to explain in clear terms the symptoms of the ailment he/she is suffering from. All the 100 respondents agreed that the francophone patients could not explain their symptoms clearly. Language as a carrier of information becomes a barrier in expression because the codes cannot be shared by the participants in the communication chart. Making efforts to diagnose their ailments could lead to inaccuracy, misinformation and assumption.

Besides the doctors, nurses and pharmacists respondents who disagreed on whether they have witnessed cases where patient's health was negatively affected due to language barrier, other respondents agreed. It is possible that ethic of secrecy guided the response of the key medical practitioners in the hospitals. However it is possible that a patient who gave wrong explanation of his symptoms and interpreted instructions wrongly could have his health affected not by negligence of the medical practitioners but by wrong information given by the patient as a result of language barrier.

There is likelihood of doctors or nurses resorting to assumptions in a situation where the patient finds it extremely difficult to explain the internal symptoms of his ailment. While 95% of the administrative staff agreed that they relied on assumption in the absence of interpretation, the nurses, doctors, pharmacists and medical laboratory scientists disagreed. The core medical practitioners at the centre of saving life would not assume the patient's ailment and presume the treatment. This underscores the resilience of the doctors who would rather ask the patient to undergo series of tests to ascertain the cause of the symptoms. This effort is time sapping and where there is shortage of doctors in the hospitals, the 'barbarian' could delay other patients in consulting the available ones.

Recognizing the danger of assumption in diagnosing a patient, all the respondents representing 100% agreed that making assumption during patient's consultation could lead to wrong diagnosis.

It was equally unanimously agreed by all the respondents that wrong prescription could emanate from miscommunication with non-native speakers such as the francophone that does not understand any other language than French or his own indigenous language. This affirms the position of *dynamicleanguage.com* ‘that language barriers in healthcare settings are linked to a range of adverse outcomes such as lower quality care, poor clinical outcomes, extended hospital stays, and heightened rates of hospital readmissions’.

It is a common practice with the francophone patients to come with companions to assist in their frailty or help with communication problem. 80% of the respondents agreed that they had seen them followed to the hospitals by their relatives or acquaintances to access health facilities in the hospitals. Others, in their experiences, had come across patients of francophone origin who stormed the hospitals all alone relying on their shaky Yoruba language or English to be attended to by the medical practitioners. On the reliability of doctors on companions to interpret for the patients, all the respondents agreed that relying on them could lead to incomplete information.

Confidentiality is one of the guiding medical ethics which could be breached by the intervention of the companion interpreters. 90% of the respondents accented to this item. This explains that the patient might even hide some information about his health problems from his companion which in turn could be difficult to easily discover by the doctors or nurses. 90% of the respondents agreed that distortion of medical facts may arise from wrong information the medical practitioners could be fed with by the patient’s companion who might not have proper understanding of the two languages involved in communicating at the hospitals.

There is need for professional French/English interpreters to cater for communication exigencies of the francophone patients to whom English or Yoruba is not a language of habitual use. Most of the respondents under different questionnaire items subscribe to this opinion. On whether the presence of such interpreters will make consultation of the medical practitioners by the patients faster and easier, 100% of the respondents agreed indicating the indispensability of having English/French interpreters in the hospitals for communication reasons. Language; signed, scripted or spoken is the only means by which thoughts are expressed and views aired. Interpreters are mediators between two or multiple languages. 90% of the respondents agreed that there is a strong need for professional English/French interpreters in hospitals in Oyo town. Professional interpreters in the hospitals should be trained in medical terminology, cultural notes and communication healthcare peculiarities. This is to enable patients receive safe and efficient care.

As code in communication chart only becomes important when the speaker and the listener are able to decode and encode, French/English interpretation in the hospitals is inevitable if the patients and the medical practitioners would engage in functional conversation. Majority of the respondents, in response to an item on the possibility of reducing medical errors if the interpreters are available, agreed that the use of French/English interpreters would reduce medical errors that could arise from misinformation. 95% agreeing with this opinion is substantial enough to affirm that information is essential to the medical practitioners in helping the patients access care without errors.

Communication is not unidirectional as the speaker and the listener could exchange roles. Where the interpreters come in between in matters of health and care, accurate communication is imperative to save the lives of patients. On the item poser that professional interpreters will help to ensure accurate communication between health workers and francophone patients, 80% of the respondents agreed that the interpreters must be professional. This explains that not all bilingual

French/English speakers could be considered as professional interpreters of medical issues. In technical translation, the technical translators of medical terminologies should be familiar with medical terms, expression of signs and symptoms of ailments, external and internal parts of the body and expression of feelings. All these factors would help in accurate communication of the interpreters of the patients to the health workers.

Healthcare delivery would be said to be effective when the patients' needs are met. 90% of the respondents agreed that the presence of professional French/English interpreters will improve francophone patients' satisfaction and healthcare delivery. Interpreters as middlemen are at the center of ensuring such satisfaction through the correctness of the messages passed from the patients to the medical practitioners and other health workers and vice versa. Accessing healthcare services in the state hospitals in Oyo town is non-racial and no prejudicial. The francophone patients that access the facilities enjoy the same care as the natives. As could be observed in the hospitals, there is nothing to suggest the presence of quacks or auxiliary health workers in the hospitals.

Conclusion

The creation of interpretation unit for French speakers in Oyo State Hospitals in Oyo town is an urgent need. The study has been able to examine the imperatives of interpreting from French to English at the selected state hospitals in Oyo town and affirm that interpreters play major roles in ensuring proper communication of the complaints of the francophone patients' on their health to hospital workers. Proper information is very essential as basis for diagnosis of any ailment by the medical practitioners. Understanding French speakers who come to the hospitals to access health facilities with no or shaky knowledge of English or native language becomes a herculean task for health workers without a professional interpreter who is vast in the use of the two or three languages.

Majority of the francophone people in question contribute significantly to the economic development of the state as they engage in large farming activities and trading in agricultural produce. This makes their effective occupation of farmlands a boost to the economic efforts of the state government. Hence, the need to pay adequate attention to their health needs enhanced by effective communication in the language they understand.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are hereby proposed:

- i. Trained interpreters in French/English with at least a degree of master in translation studies with bias for technical translation should be employed by Oyo state government and deployed to all the state hospitals in Oyo state in general and to Oyo town in particular;
- ii. The recruited interpreters should be made to undergo diploma courses in medical terminologies;
- iii. Workshops and seminars should be organized for medical practitioners and interpreters on synergy between interpreters and medical workers on health care delivery to patients who are non-native speakers of the indigenous languages;
- iv. Basic facilities such as office equipment, furniture, bookshelf stocked with relevant materials on practice of interpretation should be provided;

- v. The interpretation unit should be well labeled in every hospital and francophone patients should always be encouraged to express their health needs freely with the interpreters.

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